

Knowledge and Attitude towards Homosexuality among College Students in selected Colleges of Rewa (M.P): A Descriptive Study

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Abstract

Homosexuality is attraction between the same sex peoples. A person's sexual instinct (inborn pattern of romantic and sexual interest and identity) affects the attitudes of others toward him or her. In this time heterosexuality is the standard and most minority groups (counting lesbian Women and gay men) are subjected to stereotypes. The number of people associated with same-sex sexual activities ranges from 4 to 17%.¹The aim of the study is to assess knowledge and attitude towards homosexuality among college students. A non experimental descriptive survey research design was adopted. 100 college students were selected through purposive sampling technique. The standardized questionnaires were used for the data collection that is Knowledge about Homosexuality Questionnaire (KHQ) and Homosexuality Attitude Scale (HAS). Data was analyzed by using SPSS 20.0 version. The findings showed that the socio demographic variables of college students was found that the majority of 53(53.0%) were in the age group of 20-22 years, 69 (69.0%) of them were female, most of the students 85(85.0%) were Hindus, 93(93%) of students were unmarried, 33(33.0%) were III year students and most of the college students 90 (90.0%) received information towards homosexuality through mass media. Findings related to knowledge 63(63%) students had an average knowledge, 31(31%) had poor knowledge and 6 (6%) had good knowledge towards homosexuality. The attitude of college students towards homosexuality was found to be favorable. In the study 90(90%) of the college students had favorable attitude and 10 (10%) college students had unfavorable attitude towards homosexuality. There was significant association between knowledge score and demographic variables like age of the students and year of study where as no significant association between knowledge score and demographic variables like gender, religion, marital status and source of previous knowledge. The association between socio- demographic variables and attitude score. There was significant association between attitude score and demographic variables like age of the students and year of study where as no significant association between attitude score and demographic variables like gender, religion, marital status and source of previous knowledge.

Keywords: Homosexuality, Attitude, Knowledge, College and College Students.

Introduction

Homosexuality is not a specific phenomenon. In a few societies individuals are for the most part not happy in uncovering their gay orientation and that's the reason the pervasiveness of homosexuality is hard to find out in community based studies.

Around the world, it is assessed at 2-4% of the population. Social culturally, homosexuality is still for the most part not seen as normalization.²

Herman (2014) stated that transgender people confront social stigma and stress by connecting of minority have issue of separation and face physical and psychological violence. These experiences have cause to suicidality of transgender individuals. The findings from the NTD Survey, a huge convenience sample of transgender individuals, recommended that rates of transgender discrimination are high: Around 78% of those surveyed report experience direct abuse or segregation in the workplace.⁵

In 2010, Worldwide LGBT persons experience tremendous amount of discrimination, provocation and exploitation from society. Likewise, many places in the

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globe do not give a safe environment for people of sexual minorities to live and convey their orientation freely. The United Nations reports that in more than 70 countries, laws make it a crime to be homosexual so it presenting millions to the risk of arrest; and imprisonment.⁶

LGBT people having negative experiences with health care professionals including encountering homophobia and conveyance of unacceptable treatment. As a result LGBT individuals can be hesitate to reveal their sexual characteristics when looking for health care services and may not get proper health Care for themselves and their families.⁷

Objectives

1. To assess knowledge and attitude towards homosexuality among college students.
2. To find out the association between knowledge and attitude towards homosexuality with their selected socio demographic variables.

Hypothesis

- H_0 –There will be no significant association between knowledge and attitude with selected socio- demographic variables.
- H_1 –There will be significant association between knowledge and attitude with selected socio- demographic variables.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research approach was used in the study. The sample size consists of 100 college students

SECTION –A

FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF COLLEGE STUDENTS ACCORDING TO SOCIO- DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

Fig 01 Bar Diagram Representing the Percentage Distribution of College Student According to Age

from selected colleges of Rewa (M.P.). Non probability purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the participants. The instrument used for the study consists of **Part A-** Socio demographic Data, **Part B-** Knowledge about Homosexuality Questionnaire (KHQ) developed by Harris, Nightengale and Owen, is a 20-item true/false questionnaire used to assess the knowledge of college students towards homosexuality and **Part C-** Homosexuality Attitude Scale (HAS) created by, Marry E Kite and Kay Deaux, is a 21-Likert scale used to assess the attitude of college students towards homosexuality. The knowledge and attitude of college students towards Homosexuality was assessed & compared with the socio – demographic variables by using descriptive & inferential statistics.

Results

The data were organized & presented under following sections.

Section I: Distribution of socio demographic variables of college students.

Section II: Description of knowledge of college students towards homosexuality.

Section III: Description of attitude of college students towards Homosexuality.

Section IV: Association between the socio demographic variables and knowledge of college students.

Section V: Association between the socio demographic variables and attitude of college students.

Fig No. 02 Pie Diagram Representing the Percentage Distribution of College Students According Gender

Fig No. 03 Bar Diagram Representing the Percentage Distribution of College Student According to Religion

Fig. No. 04 Bar Diagram Representing the Percentage Distribution of College Student According to Marital Status.

Fig no. 05 Bar Diagram Representing the Percentage Distribution of College Student According to Monthly Income of Family

Fig no. 06 Bar Diagram Representing the Percentage Distribution of College Student According to Year of Study

Fig No. 07 Bar diagram representing the percentage distribution of college students according to Source of Previous Knowledge

SECTION-B

DESCRIPTION OF KNOWLEDGE OF COLLEGE STUDENTS TOWARDS HOMOSEXUALITY

Fig No: 08 Pie diagram representing the distribution of college students according to Knowledge

SECTION III

DESCRIPTION OF ATTITUDE OF COLLEGE STUDENTS TOWARDS HOMOSEXUALITY

Fig No: 09 Pie diagram representing the distribution of college students according to Attitude

SECTION IV

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THE SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND KNOWLEDGE SCORE OF COLLEGE STUDENTS

Table No - 01: Association between knowledge score and age of college students

Age of students	Knowledge about Homosexuality			Total	Chi square	P value
	Poor	Average	Good			
17-19 Years	16 69.6%	7 30.4%	0 0%	23 100%	26.327	<0.0001 S
20-22 Years	10 18.9%	41 77.4%	2 3.8%	53 100%		
23-25 Years	5 20.8%	15 62.5%	4 16.7%	24 100%		
Total	31 31%	63 63%	6 6%	100 100%		

Table No-02: Association between knowledge score and gender of college students

Gender	Knowledge about Homosexuality			Total	Chi square	P value
	Poor	Average	Good			
Male	7 22.6%	22 71%	2 6.5%	31 100%	1.495	0.473 NS
Female	24 34.8%	41 59.4%	4 5.8%	69 100%		
Total	31 31%	63 63%	6 6%	100 100%		

Table No - 03: Association between knowledge score and religion of college students

Religion	Knowledge about Homosexuality			Total	Chi square	P value
	Poor	Average	Good			
Hindu	26 30.6%	54 63.5%	5 5.9%	85 100%	7.798	0.099 NS
Muslim	1 10%	8 80%	1 10%	10 100%		
Christian	4 80%	1 20%	0 0%	5 100%		
Total	31 31%	63 63%	6 6%	100 100%		

Table No-04: Association between knowledge score and marital status of college students

Marital status	Knowledge about Homosexuality			Total	Chi square	P value
	Poor	Average	Good			
Unmarried	31 33.3%	56 60.2%	6 6.5%	93 100%	4.421	0.110 NS
Married	0 0%	7 100%	0 0%	7 100%		
Total	31 31%	63 63%	6 6%	100 100%		

Table No - 05: Association between knowledge score and year of study of college students

Year of study	Knowledge about Homosexuality			Total	Chi square	P value
	Poor	Average	Good			
First year	11 78.6%	3 21.4%	0 0%	14 100%	26.510	<0.0001* S
Second year	10 45.5%	12 54.5%	0 0%	22 100%		
Third year	7 21.2%	23 69.7%	3 9.1%	33 100%		
Fourth year	3 9.7%	25 80.6%	3 9.7%	31 100%		
Total	31 31%	63 63%	6 6%	100 100%		

Table No-06 : shows that Association between knowledge score and Source of previous knowledge

Source of previous knowledge	Knowledge about Homosexuality			Total	Chi square	P value
	Poor	Average	Good			
Friend	4 40%	5 50%	1 10%	10 100%	0.885	0.643 NS
Mass media	27 30%	58 64.4%	5 5.6%	90 100%		
Total	31 31%	63 63%	6 6%	100 100%		

SECTION V

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THE SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND ATTITUDE OF COLLEGE STUDENTS.

Table No - 07: Association between attitude score and age of college students

Age	Attitude towards homosexuality		Total	Chi square	P value
	Unfavorable attitude	Favorable attitude			
17-19 Years	6 26.1%	17 73.9%	23 100%	9.634	0.008* S
20-22 Years	4 7.5%	49 92.5%	53 100%		
23-25 Years	0 0%	24 100%	24 100%		
Total	10 10%	90 90%	100 100%		

Table No -08: Association between attitude score and gender of college students

Gender	Attitude towards homosexuality		Total	Chi square	P value
	Unfavorable attitude	Favorable attitude			
Male	4 12.9%	27 87.1%	31 100%	0.421	0.517 NS
Female	6 8.7%	63 91.3%	69 100%		
Total	10 10%	90 90%	100 100%		

Table No - 09: Association between attitude score and religion of college students

Religion	Attitude towards homosexuality		Total	Chi square	P value
	Unfavorable attitude	Favorable attitude			
Hindu	7 8.2%	78 91.8%	85 100%	1.961	0.375 NS
Muslim	2 20%	8 80%	10 100%		
Christian	1 20.0%	4 80%	5 100%		
Total	10 10%	90 90%	100 100%		

Table No- 10: Association between attitude score and marital status of college students

Marital status	Attitude towards homosexuality		Total	Chi square	P value
	Unfavorable attitude	Favorable attitude			
Unmarried	10 10.8%	83 89.2%	93 100%	0.836	0.360 NS
Married	0 0%	7 100%	7 100%		
Total	10 10%	90 90%	100 100%		

Table No - 11: shows that Association between attitude score and year of study of college students

Year of study	Attitude towards homosexuality		Total	Chi square	P value
	Unfavorable attitude	Favorable attitude			
First year	4 28.6%	10 71.4%	14 100%	14.550	0.002* S
Second year	5 22.7%	17 77.3%	22 100%		
Third year	1 3%	32 97%	33 100%		
Fourth year	0 0%	31 100%	31 100%		
Total	10 10%	90 90%	100 100%		

Table No - 12: shows that Association between attitude score and Source of previous knowledge of college students

Source of previous knowledge	Attitude towards homosexuality		Total	Chi square	P value
	Unfavorable attitude	Favorable attitude			
Friend	1 10.0%	9 90.0%	10 100.0%	0.00	1.000 NS
Mass media	9 10.0%	81 90.0%	90 100.0%		
Total	10 10.0%	90 90.0%	100 100.0%		

Conclusion

- The present study revealed that the college students have average knowledge and most of the students have favorable attitude towards homosexuality.
- The present study showed that majority of college students had knowledge 56(56%) in Gay men are more likely to be victims of violent crime than the general public, Homosexual activity occurs in many animals and one difference between homosexual men and women is that lesbians tend to have more partners over their lifetime. majority of college students had favorable attitude 68 (68%) in finding out that an artist was gay would have no effect on my appreciation of his/ her work.
- There is significant association between knowledge score and demographic variable like age and year of study regarding homosexuality. There is no significant association between knowledge score and other demographic variables.
- There is significant association between attitude score and demographic variable like age of students and year of study. There is no significant association between attitude score and other demographic variables.

Reference

1. Grabovac I, Abramovic M, Komlenovic G, Milosevic M, Mustajbegovic J. Attitudes and Knowledge about Homosexuality among Medical Students in Zagreb. *Coll Antropol.* 2014; vol (38): issue (1):39.
2. Reddy S, Reddy P, Quadri M, Ohri N, Desai S. Attitude towards Homosexuality among Psychiatrists in India. *Archives of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy.* 2016; vol (3):32-33.
3. Flores AR. Attitude towards transgender right: perceived knowledge and secondary interpersonal contact. 2015; 3(3):398-400.
4. Doug M. Violence against LGBT people. Rutgers University Press. 2015. Assessed on 15/10/2017
5. Chapman R, Zappia T, Nicol P, Shields L. Nursing and medical students' attitude, knowledge and beliefs regarding lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender parents seeking health care for their children. *J Clin Nurs.* 2011;21:45-47.
6. Wah Kong Lau. Survey on public attitude towards homosexuality in Hong Kong. *Home Affairs Bureau.* 2006:1-42. Assessed on 4/4/2018
7. Herek GM. Beyond homophobia: a social psychological perspective on attitudes towards lesbians and gay men. *J Homosex.* 2005; vol (10): issue (1-2):1-21.
8. Osmanaga Fatbardha. Students Attitudes towards Homosexuality .*European Scientific Journal.* 2015; vol (11): issue (23):170-174.
9. Sargin Nurten, Circir Osman. The Attitudes of Prospective Teachers towards Homosexuality. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies.* 2015; vol (1): issue (1): 17-18.
10. Picketl, Brent. The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. Available from : <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/homosexuality/> / assessed on 5/5/2018

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